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Trend and Performance of Agricultural Production in India Dr. V. Nachimuthu and R. Uma Maheswari	99
Jain Philosophy of Kundakunda Acharya Dr. T. Suryaprakash	103
Empowerment of Rural Women through DWCRA in Rural Areas B. Dorababu	107
Infant and Child Mortality in India: A Geospatial Analysis G. Sivanna	112
Women in Professional Education: An Overview M. Kumaraswamy and Dr. K.V. Amarnath	115
Ideas of Loknayak Jayaprakash Narayan: An Overview Dr. T. Nageswara Naidu	119
User Satisfaction on Library Resources and Services in Madanapalle Institute of Technology & Sciences, Madanapalle: A study in Andhra Pradesh Dr. D. Ravinder	122
Functional Disability among Elderly in an Urban Setting of Tamil Nadu: Prevalence, Correlates and Determinants Phamila Jesintha Rajee	126

Contributors

Notes to Contributors

WOMEN IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION: AN OVERVIEW

M. Kumaraswamy* and Dr. K.V. Amarnath**

ABSTRACT

Status of women in India has been different during different periods of time. In the Vedic period (4000 BC-1500 BC) the position of women was respectable and her role effective. The post-Vedic period (1500 BC - 500 BC) show that the women's position improved with respect to holding a property. The last century saw a paradigm shift in the status of women from being a weaker sex to equal sex. The first effort to empower women on the global level was made in 1975, the year which was observed as the International women's year with the motto Equality, Development and peace. From the year 1975 till the year 1985 it was declared as women's decade. From the year 1995 till the year 2005 it was declared as women's decade.

INTRODUCTION

In recognition of the importance of establishing gender equality around the world, the United Nations Development Fund for Women's (UNIFEM) was established as a separate fund with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 1984. At that time, the general assembly instructed it to "ensure women's involvement with mainstream activities." The platform of action resulting from the 1995 Beijing world conference on women expanded this concept, calling it "gender mainstreaming" - i.e. the application of gender perspective to all legal and social norms and standard, to all policy development, research, planning, advocacy, development, implementation and monitoring - as a mandate for all member states. It is a known fact that in spite of a very well formulated policy of positive discrimination, the representation of dalit and adwasi students is not adequate and the proportion of women from among them is negligible. They generally join general education courses and are denied access to elite courses and institutions. In 2001-02, the proportions of SC/ST students were much less as compared to students of general categories. There were 824 SC women and 344 ST women, i.e. 4.3 percent and 1.8 percent respectively of all women research students. They are also better represented in states in which women have better representation and in which higher education facilities have expanded in recent years. In every societies there are in some form or the other status - groups based on power, privileges prestige. (Maciver and Page, 1923) the formation of higher and lower status and inequality in the distribution of power and privileges can be regarded as social stratification (Bottomore, T.B., 1978). The norms regarding social groups based on power, privileges and prestige, lead to formation of higher and lower status societal positions based on social inequality (Ghurye G.S., 1999). From the point of view of enjoying power and privileges were differently ranked groups having their respective status in society. Those who have more power and privileges belong to higher social status and vice-versa.

EDUCATION AS SOCIAL PHENOMENA

The caste system based on notions of purity and pollution believed that the scheduled Caste were impure and branded them "Untouchables". From this notion flowed all the disabilities and denials of not only economic rights, but also social, cultural and political rights to Scheduled Castes the Scheduled Caste for excluded from main stream society, suffered stigma and discrimination lived in poverty and remained as marginalized groups. Knowledge as one of the greatest human virtues has been immensely valued in Indian society and its acquisitions and dissemination considered as a service of highest order throughout the ages. During the ancient period, the sams and seers of India showed the world the path of truth, wisdom, and peace. The modern concept of a university is close to that of forest ashram institutions in the ancient Hindu tradition of adult learning. It is recorded that as far back as 1500 BC Indian teachers would retire to clearings in the forest along with groups of young men who volunteered to join them in living a life of contemplation and philosophical discussion (Fletcher, 1968). Such ashram schools, when grew in number and size and attracted learners from far and wide, took the shape of corporate institutions. Buddhist centres of learning at Takshashila (5th century AD)-the oldest university of the world with over 10,500 students, and Nalanda (12th century AD) with 10,000 students and 1,500 teachers are examples of ancient Indian universities (Narlikar, 2003). These were in fact, IITs and MITs of those days.

Indian society is stratified on the basis of caste hierarchy, religious affiliation, linguistic diversity, and regional loyalty. A large majority of people professes Vedic Dharma - a religion popularly termed as Hinduism. Traditionally, Hindu society has been divided by Jati Pratha (Caste System), which has strongest historical roots and is mainly based on traditional family vocations on the principle of division of labour. While grouping people into 1600 of castes and sub castes reflecting their socio economic, educational, and cultural disparities, caste

Research Scholar* & Teaching Personnel**, Dept. of Sociology, S.K. University, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh, India

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system has recently acquired very strong political dimensions (Chauhan, 2008) with various caste combinations emerging to form three major socio economic categories - Forward Castes (FCs), Scheduled Castes & Scheduled Tribes (SCs/STs), and Other Backward Castes (OBCs). Because of nature of their work and the lowest rank in the caste hierarchy, SCs remained disadvantaged and could not benefit from the available opportunities of development in various socio economic fields including education. The STs are those people who live in geographically isolated remote areas such as forest and hilly tracks, largely cut-off from mainstream society. Most of them are secluded and culturally disadvantaged due to poor transformation and communication facilities and have also remained deprived of opportunities in all fields of development. These two sections of society have always been a focus of government attention, especially during the post -independence period. In addition, some castes among OBCs, those not among the poor, are also classified as educationally backward.

The process of globalisation has transformed world trade, communications, educational activities and economic relations since the latter part of 20th century. Student's option for higher education is no longer constrained by national boundaries. For the first time in history in the era of globalization, world's student population truly have access to a 'global market place' of higher education. with the dramatic rise of a new Indian upper class, the number of students who are able to pursue education in other countries has really increased. It has led to very rapid integration of countries across the globe in terms of commodities as well as finance. However, the first three modern universities at Calcutta, Bombay, and Madras were established in 1857 as examining bodies for existing 25 colleges and modelled on the lions of the University of London. It was from this point onwards that higher-education system grew steadily in size, especially due to the national freedom struggle, which gained strength and momentum in the first quarter of 20th century. In 1947, there were 20 universities with 500 colleges enrolling about 100,000 students. The system has continued to develop with accelerated rate during the last six decades (1947-2007) and has become third largest in the world, next only to China and the USA, with 431 Universities, 21,000 Colleges, 12 million students and 505,000 teachers (Thorat, 2008). Indian universities and colleges account for over 10% of the total enrollment in Higher-education institutions in the world, but still it is too small to accommodate 138 million domestic youth in the age-group of 18-24 years. The reported gross enrollment ratio (GER) of 56% for developed countries. The government of India proposes to increase the GER to 15% by year 2012 and to 21% by 2017 through large-scale expansion of the system by way of opening new institutions.

HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

Higher Education was entrusted with the responsibility of protecting the constitutional provisions for positive discrimination. The commitment to broaden the student base was reflected in the financial incentives provided to dalit and adivasi students. Higher Education has occupied a dominant position in independent India science it was perceived as a promoter of economic growth, technological development and a tool of equal opportunity and upward social mobility. There is a direct nexus between the industry, corporate world and higher education, which has brought a transformation in the skills needed for jobs. There has been a corresponding change in the boundaries between Arts and Science subjects. Pure Science are relegated to a lower position than are the applied science and professional Skills. In the hierarchy of disciplines, new disciplines such as management, Media and Mass communication, Fashion Technology have also risen up the ladder. Women used to Take admission in General Education or in Arts, Humanities and social science till the early 1990's-a trend which is still continuing. However, they are also entering the professional subjects offered in the public and private institutions in the traditionally labelled 'masculine disciplines'. The impact of these changes requires attention if the goal of social change and gender equality has to be achieved. Feminist sociological perspectives on women's educational experience have highlighted several dimensions like their under participation, under achievement and under representation; sex Role socialization and stereotyping of the feminine role and its impact upon the girl's Education. The segregation of girls into streams of Arts and Humanities and boys into science At the school level is well known. Sociologists were of the opinion that this imbalance in subjects had to be redressed to remove inequality. In India, the decision to make science compulsory up to 10th class ensured that all girls will also study Science. Much has been written on the patriarchal imprint on the subject choices of women in higher education and on the feminine and masculine dichotomy of subjects.

There are several dimensions of changes that have taken place since 1991, the most important being the entry of private institutions, the increase in the individual cost of higher education, the entry of foreign institutions, the large number of Indian students who go abroad on self financing basis, change in academic environment of higher educational institutions. There is a perceptible change in the choices of women especially in the metropolitan Cities Where they are enrolling in the new 'professional' courses such as Fashion Designing, Computers, Human Resource Management etc. This helped in giving important to social justice around the issues of caste, tribe, class and gender. There has been a care full articulation of education for equality for women Which is reflected in the educational policy in post independence India since 1991, the policies of government have dramatically changed the otherwise privileged position of higher education. The Govt. Began to talk of setting aside public support to higher education and to make itself-financing while privatizing it. Higher education has also become a non merit good. Private institutions have been permitted to be set up on a liberal scale without a clearly defined policy to regulate them (Anandhkrishnan, 2004). the link of universities with

private sector is not new in India nor is the nexus between the higher education and economy. What is disheartening is the nature and speed of change, the motives of those who are establishing the private institutions, the lack of the response from the Indian government. It is sad to note that though India's population is above 100 Crores, its access to higher Education is still about 6% as compared to 88% in U.S.A, 52% in U.K, 19% in Thailand and 11% in Indonesia.

STREAMING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The programmes in higher education are divided into those of general subjects such as arts which included Social Sciences and Humanities; Pure Sciences, Professional Courses such as Engineering, Medical Science, Teacher Education, Agriculture, Law etc. They are also divided into masculine and feminine disciplines. Arts, Social Science, Humanity teacher education have been viewed feminine disciplines. On the other hand, Commerce, Law, Engineering are masculine Subjects. Medical Sciences has not been a masculine disciplines in India unlike in the western countries. In India like in the rest of south Asia, The practice of female seclusion enjoined the treatment of women doctors, thereby enabling them to enter the medical profession (Chanana, 1988). The proportion of women in some of the masculine disciplines was very less soon after independence and remained so till the 1980's. With the exception of commerce. Science, a masculine discipline provides an interesting insight on disciplinary choices of young men and women. The proportion of men in science subjects was 80-90% in 1980-81 which has come down to 59.8% in 2002-03. The differential importance of general science for women and men over time has to be understood as a background to shifts in disciplinary choices in the recent past. The proportion of women in Sciences decreased from 33.3 percent in 1950-51 to 28.8% in 1980-81. has never been the first preference for young women whose parents considered marriage much more important than higher education. A science degree required a longer investment of time and other resources and thus was not desirable. Prior to 1990's, education and its linkage to the job market early on in life was only for those men who needed jobs and was certainly not for women. These days' young women and men like to earn as soon as they can, even while in school. The revolution in values cuts across upper and middle strata, who want to begin earning as soon as possible. The daughters of city based professional parents, especially if they do not have brothers, have really undergone a great change. The parents are giving the best education to their daughters and expect them to be independent and follow carriers. In this changed scenario, the priorities of women have also changed. They too want professional education and are therefore entering into masculine disciplines. The two simultaneous trends of clustering /Concentration and dispersal can be seen in the enrollment of men and women in higher education. During the first three decades, while women tended to be clustered in the general disciplines of arts and sciences (nearly 90%) men's participation was characterized by both clustering in Arts and Sciences disciplines but also significantly dispersed in others such as Commerce, Engineering/Technical and Law. Lately, the women's participation too is marked by clustering as well as dispersal. Once women enter higher education at the under graduate level, their chances of going up to the next level increases. This may also have to do with the master's programme in Management, Computers and IT, Media, Advertising, Fashion Technology etc. Which are popular in the metropolitan cities.

The gender impact of social, cultural and economic disparities across states has been referred to time and again by the official committees and commissions as well as by the social scientists. These trends are continuing while the enrollment of women varies from province to province. Kerala has had the highest enrollment and even now it is 60 Percent. Thus, there are more women than men in higher education. The other states where they are more than half the proportion are Goa (58.05), Punjab (52.68), Andaman and Nicobar Islands (57.77), Chandigarh (55.05) and Pondicherry (52.06). Those with lower proportion are also the most backward namely Bihar (23.81), Jharkhand (30.40), Chhattisgarh (36.70), Rajasthan (32.33), Uttar Pradesh (38.40) and Madhya Pradesh (37.20). In these provinces, the proportion is less than the all India average of 40.05 percent. The link between the state and professional education is very close. The variations can be seen in the growth of engineering and technology courses in the four southern states. A majority of women students were from the southern and western regions. The number of women students is highest in the states of Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. The regional disparities are due to several reasons. One of them is early starting of formal education in the southern as compared to the northern regions during the colonial period. Many private engineering colleges have been established there. The socio-cultural practices and positive attitudes of parents towards the higher education of their daughters also has an impact on the women's access to professional education. This difference is to a large extent due to the practice of female seclusion in the north and its absence in the south (Chanana, 1988).

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